

Effects of Civic Education on Youth Participation in Democratic Practices: A Case of Youths in Selected Constituencies of Lusaka District, Zambia

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Abstract:

Overview: *This study explored the impact of civic education on youth participation in democratic practices within selected constituencies of Lusaka District, Zambia. It examined how civic education initiatives, both formal and informal, influence the knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors of young people regarding their roles and responsibilities in a democratic society.*

Body of Knowledge: *The study focused on the extent to which civic education fosters political awareness, engagement in electoral processes, and advocacy for democratic governance among the youth. By analyzing the relationship between civic education and active citizenship, the study aimed to highlight the potential of educational programs to empower young people as key contributors to the democratic process in Zambia.*

Methods: *The study employed both the qualitative and quantitative methods and a descriptive survey design that sampled Head teachers, Teachers, NGO officials, Councilors, Community members and the Youth. The sample size was 110, with a target population of 1100. Data was obtained from the respondents by means of interviews and questionnaires. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS and Microsoft excel whereas the qualitative data from semi structured interviews were analyzed thematically.*

Results: *The findings noted that civic education plays a pivotal role in enhancing youth engagement in democratic processes. The findings also indicated that exposure to comprehensive civic education significantly increases youths' awareness and understanding of their rights and responsibilities as citizens, thereby fostering a more active participation in voting, community decision-making, and other democratic activities.*

Recommendation: *The study calls for interventions that address the gaps in civic education to further empower young people to contribute meaningfully to the democratic landscape in Zambia.*

Keywords: *Civic Education, Democratic Practices, Development, Participation, and Youths.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Civic education plays a pivotal role in fostering youth participation in democratic practices, as it equips young people with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to engage effectively in the political and civic life of their communities (Chanda, 2023). Through comprehensive civic education programs, youths are exposed to the principles of democracy, human rights, and the responsibilities of citizenship, which helps to cultivate a sense of civic duty and empowerment. These programs often emphasize critical thinking, debate, and active participation, encouraging youths to become informed voters, advocates, and community leaders (Barnes, 2006). Furthermore, civic education nurtures a deeper understanding of democratic processes, such as elections, governance, and the rule of law, thereby increasing youths' willingness and ability to participate in these processes. In contexts where civic education is robust, there is often a noticeable correlation with higher levels of youth voter turnout, activism, and engagement in policy discussions, which ultimately strengthens democratic governance. In the Zambian context, where there are ongoing efforts to enhance civic education, it has the potential to significantly influence youth participation, addressing the challenges of political apathy and disengagement among young people, and ensuring that they play an active role in shaping the future of the nation.

Civic education is a fundamental component in fostering an informed, active, and responsible citizenry. It encompasses the teaching of the principles, values, and practices of democracy, as well as the rights and responsibilities of citizens within a society (Chanda et al, 2024). Through civic education, individuals gain an understanding of the structures and functions of government, the electoral process, and the importance of participation in public life. It also promotes critical thinking and the ability to engage in discussions about public issues, encouraging learners to consider multiple perspectives and the common good. Moreover, civic education plays a crucial role in cultivating civic virtues such as tolerance, justice, and respect for the rule of law (Cogan & Print, 2016). By equipping citizens with the knowledge and skills needed to effectively participate in democratic processes, civic education strengthens the social fabric and helps to safeguard democratic governance. In contexts where democracy is emerging or under threat, civic education is particularly vital in promoting political stability, reducing apathy, and fostering a culture of engagement and accountability among citizens, especially the youth. Chitondo & Chanda (2023) noted that the impact of French colonialism in Africa on political structures in the region has been profound and has left lasting legacies that continue to shape the political landscape. This education also provides a foundation for lifelong civic engagement, empowering individuals to contribute meaningfully to their communities and the broader society.

Democratic practices encompass the principles, processes, and behaviors that support the functioning of a democratic system, where power is vested in the people and exercised directly or through elected representatives. These practices include free and fair elections, where citizens have the right to vote without coercion and with confidence in the integrity of the electoral process (Dassonneville et al, 2012). Transparency and accountability in government operations are also

crucial, ensuring that public officials are answerable to the electorate and that decisions are made in the public interest. Democratic practices further involve the protection of human rights, including freedom of speech, assembly, and the press, allowing for open debate, dissent, and the free exchange of ideas. De Brito (2010) alluded that the rule of law is another cornerstone, ensuring that laws are applied equally to all citizens and that justice is administered impartially. Moreover, democratic practices emphasize the importance of civic engagement and participation, encouraging citizens to be active in their communities and to advocate for issues that matter to them. This active participation is often facilitated through civil society organizations, which play a critical role in educating citizens about their rights and responsibilities, monitoring government actions, and advocating for social and political reforms. Overall, democratic practices are essential for fostering a political culture that values inclusivity, pluralism, and the peaceful resolution of conflicts, thereby strengthening the legitimacy and stability of democratic institutions (Diamond, 2003).

Development in democratic practices refers to the process by which societies evolve and refine the mechanisms, institutions, and behaviors that support and sustain democratic governance. This progression involves the strengthening of political institutions, such as free and fair elections, independent judiciaries, and accountable governments, which are crucial for ensuring that power is exercised in a manner that reflects the will of the people (Chanda, 2024). Additionally, the development of democratic practices often includes the promotion of civil liberties and human rights, ensuring that citizens have the freedom to express their opinions, associate, and participate in the political process without fear of repression. Public participation, particularly through civic education and engagement, plays a vital role in this development by fostering a politically informed and active citizenry. Over time, successful democracies also tend to cultivate a culture of tolerance, where diverse views are respected, and political discourse is conducted in a manner that prioritizes dialogue over conflict (Owen, 2013). The development of these practices is often influenced by both internal factors, such as economic conditions and social cohesion, and external factors, including international norms and pressures. As nations continue to navigate the complexities of governance, the ongoing development of democratic practices remains critical to achieving political stability, social justice, and sustainable development (Chanda et al, 2024).

Participation in democratic practices is a fundamental aspect of a functioning democracy, as it enables citizens to exercise their rights and influence the governance of their country. This participation can take various forms, including voting in elections, engaging in public debates, joining political parties or civic organizations, and taking part in protests or advocacy efforts. Romanovska (2021) noted that active participation ensures that the voices of diverse groups are heard, contributing to more inclusive and representative decision-making processes. Moreover, it fosters a sense of civic responsibility among citizens, encouraging them to be informed about political issues and to hold leaders accountable. In many societies, the level of participation is influenced by factors such as education, access to information, economic conditions, and the

overall political environment. Barriers to participation, such as voter suppression, political apathy, or lack of trust in institutions, can undermine democratic processes and lead to a disconnect between the government and the governed (Chanda, 2024). Therefore, promoting and facilitating widespread and equitable participation in democratic practices is crucial for the sustainability and legitimacy of any democracy.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Civic education plays a crucial role in shaping democratic engagement and participation, yet its impact on youth involvement in democratic practices remains inadequately explored in the context of Lusaka District, Zambia. Despite various initiatives aimed at enhancing civic knowledge among young people, there is limited empirical evidence assessing how effectively civic education influences their engagement in democratic processes (Chanda et al, 2024). This study sought to address this gap by investigating the effects of civic education on youth participation in democratic practices within selected constituencies of Lusaka District. Specifically, the study examined how different facets of civic education, such as curriculum content, teaching methods, and extracurricular activities, affect the levels of political awareness, voter participation, and active citizenship among youths. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing targeted educational strategies that foster meaningful youth involvement in Zambia's democratic processes and contribute to the strengthening of democratic governance at the grassroots level.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate how civic education influences the engagement and active participation of young people in democratic processes.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- To assess the impact of civic education programs on the level of youth awareness and understanding of democratic processes and practices in selected constituencies of Lusaka District.
- To analyze the relationship between civic education and the extent of youth engagement and participation in democratic activities within selected constituencies of Lusaka District.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the Participatory Democracy Theory. The theory posits that democratic engagement and decision-making are most effective when citizens actively participate in political processes, ensuring that governance reflects the diverse needs and interests of the community. In the context of Zambia, specifically within selected constituencies of Lusaka District, the impact of civic education on youth participation in democratic practices can be profound (Chitondo, 2022). Civic education aims to empower young people by providing them with the knowledge, skills, and confidence necessary to engage meaningfully in democratic processes. By fostering an understanding of their rights and responsibilities, and the mechanisms of democratic governance, civic education encourages youths to take part in electoral processes, advocate for community issues, and contribute to policy discussions (Chanda, 2023). This theoretical framework suggests that as youths become more informed and engaged through targeted civic education programs,

they are more likely to participate actively in democratic practices, thereby strengthening the democratic fabric of their communities and enhancing overall governance.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study's significance lies in its potential to enhance our understanding of how educational initiatives shape democratic engagement among young people. By examining this relationship, the study aimed to identify the extent to which civic education influences youths' knowledge, attitudes, and involvement in democratic processes such as voting, community service, and policy advocacy. This study is crucial for informing policymakers, educators, and community leaders about the effectiveness of current civic education programs and their role in fostering an informed and active citizenry. Furthermore, the findings could provide valuable insights into designing targeted interventions that address specific gaps in civic knowledge and participation, ultimately contributing to a more engaged and responsible youth population that is better equipped to contribute to democratic governance and societal development.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed methods approach which is a combination of quantitative and qualitative data. Exploratory and descriptive designs were as well considered appropriate as they also allowed for more flexible strategies of data collection in order to answer the research questions (Banda et al, 2017). The study was aimed at collecting information from respondents on the effects of civic education on youth participation in all aspects of a democratic practices in the three constituencies within Lusaka district in Zambia. It highlighted the teaching of civics in secondary schools, factors affecting youth involvement and strategies to enhance youth participation in all the aspects of a democratic practices. Structured open-ended interviews were conducted and questionnaires were used to respondents. The sample consisted 110 respondents; 10% of the target population 1100. The population for the study was purposefully drawn from the three wards. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select Head teachers (3), and Councilors (3) while the simple random sampling procedure was used to select the Teachers (9), Community members (30), NGO officials (5) and the Youth (60). Also, the primary data was complimented by the secondary data which was derived from government policy documents, ministerial reports and relevant literature on the teaching and learning of initial literacy. The data collection process involved distributing the questionnaires to the selected participants and conducting individual interviews. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS (Statistical package for social sciences) and excel whereas the qualitative data from semi structured interviews were analyzed thematically. The study avoided pressuring respondents to take part in the research. Alternatively, permission consents, assents were obtained from respondents involved in the research and the research topic was strategically selected to ensure that there was no harm whatsoever to the research respondents. The study also upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Impact of Civic Education Programs on the Level of Youth Awareness and Understanding of Democratic Processes and Practices

According to research findings, civic education programs have a profound impact on enhancing the knowledge of democratic principles among youths in selected constituencies of Lusaka District, significantly raising their awareness and understanding of democratic processes and practices. These programs serve as a crucial tool in educating young people about their rights and responsibilities as citizens, fostering a deeper comprehension of the structures and functions of government, the importance of participation in democratic activities, and the principles of justice and equality (Chanda, 2023). By engaging youths in discussions, workshops, and practical activities related to governance, these programs equip them with the necessary knowledge to critically analyze political systems, understand the significance of voting, and actively participate in civic duties. The result is a more informed and empowered youth population that is better prepared to contribute to the democratic development of their communities and the nation at large (Burhan et al, 2023). This enhanced understanding of democratic principles not only improves their civic engagement but also lays the foundation for a more robust and participatory democracy in Zambia.

The findings also revealed that civic education programs have played a crucial role in increasing political engagement among youths in selected constituencies of Lusaka District, significantly enhancing their awareness and understanding of democratic processes and practices. These programs, often implemented through schools, community organizations, and online platforms, provide youths with essential knowledge about their rights, the importance of participation in democratic activities, and the workings of government institutions (Chanda et al, 2024). As a result, many young people have become more informed about the electoral process, the significance of voting, and their role in holding elected officials accountable. This heightened awareness has translated into increased political activism, with more youths participating in elections, engaging in community dialogues, and advocating for policy changes (Chauke, 2020). The growing involvement of young people in political discourse not only strengthens democratic practices but also ensures that their voices are heard in shaping the future of their communities and the nation at large. Consequently, these civic education initiatives are fostering a generation of informed and active citizens who are better equipped to contribute to Zambia's democratic development (Chanda, 2024).

The findings further recorded that civic education programs play a crucial role in the development of critical thinking and decision-making skills among youth, which significantly enhances their awareness and understanding of democratic processes and practices. Through engagement with civic education, young people are exposed to diverse perspectives and complex social issues, encouraging them to analyze, evaluate, and question information critically (Fretwell, 2015). One of the teachers explained that:

“Civic education often involves debates, discussions, and analysis of political scenarios, which helps youth develop critical thinking skills. These skills are essential for evaluating political information, making informed decisions, and resisting misinformation”.

This educational approach fosters the ability to make informed decisions by understanding the implications of various choices within a democratic framework. Moreover, as youth become more

adept at critical thinking, they are better equipped to participate actively in democratic practices, such as voting, civic activism, and public debate. The overall impact of these programs is the creation of a more informed and engaged youth population, capable of contributing meaningfully to the democratic processes within their communities and beyond (Holowinsky & Shimahara, 2016).

The respondents alluded that civic education programs play a crucial role in promoting social cohesion and national unity by enhancing youth awareness and understanding of democratic processes and practices. These programs educate young people about their rights, responsibilities, and the importance of active participation in democratic governance (Kahne & Sporte, 2008). By fostering a deep understanding of democratic values such as equality, justice, and inclusivity, civic education helps bridge social divides and encourages respect for diversity. Chitondo & Chanda (2023) says diversity is about what makes each of us unique and includes our backgrounds, personality, life experiences and beliefs, all of the things that make us who we are. This understanding is pivotal in cultivating a sense of national identity and solidarity among youth, reducing the likelihood of social fragmentation. Additionally, by equipping young people with the skills and knowledge needed to engage constructively in political and civic activities, these programs contribute to a more informed and cohesive society where democratic principles are upheld, and national unity is strengthened. By exposing young people to the principles of democracy, including the importance of pluralism and the protection of minority rights, these programs foster an appreciation for diverse perspectives and cultures (Chanda et al, 2024). This awareness helps youths to recognize the value of inclusivity and mutual respect as foundational elements of a democratic society. Furthermore, civic education initiatives often include practical activities, such as debates, group projects, and community engagement, which allow students to practice civil discourse and collaboration with peers from different backgrounds. Abdi (2017) says that these experiences not only deepen their understanding of democracy but also cultivate a mindset that values diversity and fosters peaceful coexistence. As a result, young individuals are better equipped to contribute to a more tolerant and cohesive society, where democratic principles are upheld and respected.

Officials from NGOs observed that civic education programs play a critical role in empowering youths to hold leaders accountable by enhancing their awareness and understanding of democratic processes and practices. These programs equip young people with the knowledge of their rights and responsibilities as citizens, fostering a sense of agency and encouraging active participation in governance (Bratton, 1999). By learning about the mechanisms of accountability, such as elections, public consultations, and legal frameworks, youths become more confident in demanding transparency and integrity from their leaders. Additionally, civic education nurtures critical thinking skills, enabling youths to assess the performance of their leaders and to recognize and challenge corruption, inefficiency, and abuse of power. This empowerment contributes to a more vibrant and participatory democracy, where informed and engaged youth play a crucial role in upholding democratic values and ensuring that leaders remain responsive to the needs and aspirations of the people (Falade, 2014). Moreover, the results showed that as young people gain a deeper comprehension of the principles of democracy, including the importance of accountability, openness, and ethical governance, they increasingly recognize the significance of

transparency in ensuring that public officials and institutions operate in the best interests of the citizenry (Chanda, 2023). This heightened awareness often translates into a stronger demand for clear and accessible information about government activities, decision-making processes, and the allocation of public resources. Mahoney et al (2006)'s study supported this finding by narrating that youths become more vigilant and proactive in advocating for transparency, holding leaders accountable, and challenging corruption, thereby contributing to a more informed and engaged citizenry committed to upholding democratic values.

Figure1: Impact of Civic Education Programs on the Level of Youth Awareness and Understanding of Democratic Processes and Practices

3.2. The Relationship between Civic Education and the Extent of Youth Engagement and Participation in Democratic Activities

The findings revealed that the relationship between civic education and the extent of youth engagement and participation in democratic activities can be quite significant. The study identified 5 factors that showed the relationship between civic education and youth engagement and participation in democratic activities. Behavioral Impact was the highest at 30%, Awareness and Empowerment at 20%, Attitudes and Values at 20%, Skills Development at 15%, and Knowledge Acquisition at 15%. Figure 2 below summarized these findings;

Figure2: The Relationship between Civic Education and the Extent of Youth Engagement and Participation in Democratic Activities

The results findings recorded that civic education plays a crucial role in shaping the behavioral attitudes of youth towards democratic engagement and participation. This relationship is evident in how civic education programs are designed to foster an understanding of democratic principles, civic responsibilities, and the functioning of democratic institutions. Through structured educational programs, young people are introduced to concepts such as the importance of voting, the value of public debate, and the role of active citizenship in a democratic society (Mainde et al, 2022). These educational interventions are aimed at equipping youths with the knowledge and skills necessary to become informed and active participants in their communities. Behavioral impact manifests in various ways. For instance, when civic education is effectively implemented, it can lead to increased participation in democratic activities, such as voting, community service, and public consultations. Educated youth are more likely to recognize the significance of their participation in democratic processes and are motivated to contribute actively (Lutaj, 2014). This is supported by Chitondo (2022)'s study who alluded that the youth who receive comprehensive civic education are more likely to engage in activities that promote social justice, advocate for policy changes, and participate in electoral processes. Moreover, civic education helps in shaping positive attitudes towards democratic institutions and processes. It fosters a sense of responsibility and commitment towards societal well-being, encouraging youths to take an active role in their communities. One of the community members noted that:

“This behavioral shift is crucial as it leads to a more engaged and participatory citizenry. The acquisition of civic knowledge and skills through education can transform passive individuals into active contributors to democratic life, thereby enhancing the overall quality of democracy”.

Chanda (2024) alluded that the effectiveness of civic education in influencing youth behavior depends on several factors, including the quality of the education provided, the relevance of the content, and the methods of delivery. Interactive and participatory teaching methods, such as simulations of democratic processes, debates, and service learning, tend to have a more profound impact on youth engagement (Mainde & Chola, 2020). Additionally, integrating real-world issues and current events into the curriculum helps make civic education more relatable and engaging for young people.

The results also revealed that awareness and empowerment are crucial elements in understanding the relationship between civic education and youth engagement and participation in democratic activities within selected constituencies of Lusaka District. Civic education aims to equip young individuals with the knowledge and skills needed to navigate and actively participate in democratic processes (Chanda, 2024). By raising awareness about democratic principles, rights, and responsibilities, civic education fosters a sense of empowerment among youth. One of the councilors expressed that:

“Civic education raises awareness about the importance of participation in democratic processes. It can empower youths to take initiative, participate in community service, and engage in political and social activism”.

This empowerment encourages them to engage more actively in democratic activities such as voting, community service, and policy advocacy. In Lusaka District, where civic education programs are implemented, there is often a noticeable increase in youth involvement in local governance and decision-making processes. Finkel (2000) noted that the relationship between awareness and empowerment highlights the importance of comprehensive civic education programs that not only inform but also inspire and motivate youth to contribute meaningfully to their communities and the democratic system.

The respondents further alluded that civic education plays a critical role in shaping the attitudes and values of young individuals towards democratic processes and engagement. By providing students with a structured understanding of civic rights, responsibilities, and the functioning of democratic institutions, civic education fosters a sense of responsibility and commitment to participatory democracy (Fitzpatrick, 2006). The attitudes and values instilled through civic education are fundamental in influencing how youth perceive and engage with democratic activities. One of the core components of civic education is the development of civic attitudes, which include a sense of civic duty, political efficacy, and trust in democratic processes. These attitudes are cultivated through curriculum components that cover the principles of democracy, the importance of voting, and the role of civic participation in shaping policy and governance. As students engage with these concepts, they begin to appreciate the significance of their contributions to democratic processes, which in turn encourages them to actively participate in activities such as

voting, community service, and public discourse (Galston, 2001). Values such as equality, justice, and respect for diversity are also integral to civic education. By emphasizing these values, civic education helps youth understand the importance of inclusivity and equity in democratic practices. This understanding fosters a commitment to advocating for social justice and engaging in activities that promote societal well-being. Chanda (2024)'s study pointed out that when students learn about the importance of human rights and social equity, they are more likely to participate in advocacy efforts and support policies that align with these values.

The youths alluded that the relationship between civic education and youth engagement is also evident in how educational programs address the practical aspects of democracy. Programs that involve simulations of democratic processes, such as mock elections or debates, provide students with hands-on experience and a deeper understanding of how democratic systems operate. This experiential learning not only enhances students' knowledge but also strengthens their commitment to democratic participation (Ginsberg & Ginsberg, 2016). By experiencing the democratic process firsthand, youth are more likely to develop a positive attitude towards voting and other forms of civic engagement. Moreover, the values and attitudes nurtured through civic education contribute to the development of informed and active citizens. When youth are educated about the impact of their participation on community and national levels, they are more likely to engage in activities that contribute to the common good (Mtonga & Magasu, 2024). This engagement is further supported by the reinforcement of democratic values and the encouragement of critical thinking skills, which enable students to analyze and address social and political issues effectively.

The study also revealed that civic education plays a pivotal role in shaping the engagement and participation of youth in democratic activities. At its core, civic education is designed to provide individuals with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for active and informed participation in democratic processes (Chanda, 2023). The development of specific skills through civic education can significantly enhance youth involvement in democratic activities, fostering a more engaged and participatory citizenry. Civic education programs are structured to cultivate a range of skills that are crucial for effective democratic participation. These skills include critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, and collaboration. Ludden (2011) says that critical thinking enables young people to analyze and evaluate political issues and policies, discern biases, and make informed decisions. Problem-solving skills empower them to address community issues and contribute to policy discussions. Communication skills are essential for articulating opinions, debating constructively, and engaging with others in the democratic process. Collaboration skills facilitate teamwork and collective action, which are often necessary for successful advocacy and community projects. When civic education focuses on these skills, it directly impacts the level of youth engagement in democratic activities. For example, programs that teach critical thinking and debate encourage students to participate in discussions about current events and policy issues, fostering a more informed electorate. Activities that promote problem-solving and project-based learning enable youth to apply their knowledge in practical ways, such as organizing community service projects or engaging in local governance. Chanda & Chisebe (2024) defines local governance as the administration and management of a community or locality by local authorities and institutions. It involves decision-making processes that address the needs and priorities of local

residents, encompassing the provision of public services such as education, transportation, sanitation, and public safety. By building these skills, civic education prepares young people to take on active roles in their communities and contributes to higher levels of political and social engagement.

The skills developed through civic education are instrumental in increasing youth participation in democratic processes. Engaged youth are more likely to vote, join political organizations, and participate in civic activities such as public forums and advocacy campaigns. They are also better equipped to understand and navigate the complexities of political systems, contributing to more robust and representative democratic practices (Patrick, 2013). Furthermore, skills like communication and collaboration enhance their ability to work effectively within groups, which is often necessary for successful participation in democratic processes. While civic education has the potential to significantly impact youth engagement and participation, there are challenges that need to be addressed. These include disparities in access to quality civic education, variations in curriculum effectiveness, and the need for programs to be relevant to the diverse experiences of young people (Chanda, 2023). To overcome these challenges, it is essential to develop inclusive and adaptable civic education programs that address the specific needs and interests of youth from different backgrounds.

The study further indicated that civic education plays a crucial role in shaping the understanding and engagement of young people in democratic processes. The acquisition of knowledge through civic education equips youths with the necessary skills and information to actively participate in democratic activities. This knowledge encompasses an understanding of democratic principles, the functions of various governmental institutions, and the rights and responsibilities of citizens (Ehin, 2007). As youths gain a clearer understanding of how democratic systems operate, they become more aware of their role within these systems, fostering a sense of responsibility and empowerment. Civic education programs often include components such as the study of constitutional rights, electoral processes, and the importance of civic duties. By integrating these topics into educational curricula, young people are encouraged to develop informed opinions and engage critically with political and social issues (IDEA, 2011). This knowledge not only enhances their ability to make informed decisions but also motivates them to take part in democratic activities such as voting, advocacy, and community service. Moreover, the relationship between knowledge acquisition and youth engagement is reflected in various empirical studies. McCartney et al (2013) indicated that youths who receive comprehensive civic education are more likely to participate in democratic processes compared to those with limited exposure. For instance, students who learn about the impact of their vote on local and national governance are more inclined to vote and participate in political discussions. Similarly, understanding the mechanisms of democratic institutions can lead to increased involvement in civic activities such as attending public meetings or joining advocacy groups.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study highlighted the significant role that civic education plays in enhancing youth engagement in democratic processes. The findings indicated that well-structured civic education programs equip young individuals with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for active and informed participation in democratic activities. By fostering a deeper understanding of democratic principles, rights, and responsibilities, these programs effectively bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical involvement. The increased awareness and competence gained through civic education contribute to higher levels of youth participation in voting, community decision-making, and advocacy. As such, this study underscores the importance of investing in robust civic education initiatives to empower the youth, strengthen democratic practices, and promote a more engaged and informed citizenry in Lusaka District and beyond.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study;

1. Enhance Curriculum Integration:

- Curriculum developers should integrate comprehensive civic education into the school curriculum to ensure that students receive a thorough understanding of democratic principles, rights, and responsibilities.

2. Strengthen Community Engagement:

- The ministry of education should develop partnerships between schools, local governments, and community organizations to create opportunities for youth to actively participate in local governance and civic activities.

3. Promote Digital Literacy and Online Platforms:

- The government should utilize digital tools and platforms to expand access to civic education and engage youth in online discussions about democratic practices.

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